

Contributions of P. C. Rây in organic synthesis

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Abstract : During most of his career Rây was busy with his work in the inorganic chemistry area. But he also had a long-standing interest in organic synthesis which finally got expressed only in terminal years of his career. We consider in this work two of his main endeavours in this area. First, synthesis of thioketones in general and thiocamphor and some related species in particular using hydrogen sulfide under acid catalysis as the reagent. Second, his introduction of thallium fluoride as a reagent for organic fluorination. The cases of fluorocarboxylate esters, fluoroketones and some more will be cited.

Keywords : Organic synthesis, thioketones, thiocamphor, fluorocarboxylates, fluoroketone, H₂S-HCl, TlF.

Introduction

After completing his B.Sc. (1882-1885) in Edinburgh University Rây chose to do his independent D.Sc. work in the inorganic area on certain aspects of double sulfates¹⁻³ and this was completed in 1887. He was also awarded the Hope Prize and continued to work for another year on several issues. He writes in his autobiography⁴, "After taking my doctorate in inorganic chemistry, I began to make up my deficiency by reading extensively chemical literature on the organic side and taking copious notes thereof..." During 1887-1888 he also became the Vice-President of Edinburgh University Chemical Society. The Society organized lectures by faculty members and senior experts in the department. Rây delivered such a lecture on May 14, 1888 on "The carboketonic ethers of Frankland and Duppa".

This interest in organic chemistry persisted throughout Rây's career and he and his group later published among other topics a number of significant papers on the synthesis of organic sulfur and fluorine compounds from Calcutta. To conclude our series of essays on the chemical researches of Rây as cited in Ref. 3 we now present briefly this aspect of his contribution.

Aliphatic thioketones

Some general observations :

In a 1964 review article⁵ it was noted that unlike their

aromatic analogues monomeric aliphatic thioketones have been little studied because of lack of general methods of synthesis for long. The methods in vogue and their limitations are chronicled. Of particular interest to us in this essay is the use of hydrogen sulfide under acid catalysis to achieve conversion of ketone to thioketone. First introduced by Fromm and Baumann this reagent only yielded trimeric thioketones for simple aliphatic ketones^{5,6}.

In the case of monocyclic ketones like cyclopentanone, cyclohexanone etc. Fromm again reported the formation of trimeric thioketone⁷. On the other hand Sen later claimed that action of hydrogen sulfide in ethanol saturated with hydrogen chloride yielded monomeric thioketones for the above kind of cyclic ketones⁸. This method has until very recently often been quoted and described as a standard procedure for preparing aliphatic monomeric thioketones. But it was recently contradicted implying that gem-dithiols instead of thioketones are actually formed⁵.

For bicyclic aliphatic ketones like fenchone, camphor and certain other classes of ketones, authentic monomeric thioketones are however readily produced using hydrogen sulfide and acidic catalysts⁵. Our special interest is in camphor where the method was first developed in the University College of Science and Technology, Calcutta.

Thiocamphor :

Rây reported in Nature (1934) a short note to the

effect that D. C. Sen in his group has been able to synthesize thiocamphor (**1b**) in good yield by treating camphor (**1a**) with hydrogen sulfide and hydrogen chloride gases in cold ethanol⁹. The details were published by Sen independently next year¹⁰.

In his paper Sen summarized the earlier methods and attempts by others which at best produced thiocamphor in small amounts and then in impure forms. In his method dry hydrogen sulfide (reagent) and hydrogen chloride (catalyst) gases were passed through a solution of racemic camphor in absolute ethanol cooled to 0 °C for several hours till the solution colour became deep red. On processing the reaction mixture *racemic* thiocamphor was isolated in 50% yield as a red crystalline solid. On similar treatment *levo* camphor afforded the same *racemic* thiocamphor. On the other hand *dextro*-camphor afforded *levo*-thiocamphor which is an important compound in several ways and its X-ray structure was determined by later workers¹¹.

Sen proposed a mechanism of the observed carbonyl to thiocarbonyl conversion via formation of a unstable hydrochloride intermediate (C(OH)(Cl)) which then becomes a hydro sulfide (C(OH)(SH)) losing water to yield the thiocarbonyl (CS). In modern terms it translates to the essentially correct events involving electrophilic (by H⁺) and nucleophilic (by HS⁻) attacks on the polarized carbonyl function followed by water elimination. Apart from defining the successful method of synthesis of thiocamphor, Sen also succeeded in reducing thiocamphor to thioborneol using zinc and ethanolic hydrogen chloride in the cold as the reducing agent¹⁰. Later he reported on the similar synthesis of thiofenchone¹² (**2b**) by the Rây-Sen method⁸ from fenchone (**2a**).

Later chemists have devised other methods based on new reagents for converting ketones to thioketones in better and better yields. For example treating bis (tricyclohexyltin) sulfide with boron trichloride in the presence of carbonyl compounds converts the carbonyl unit into its thiocarbonyl analogue in high yield. Thus camphor and fenchone are converted to the thioanalogues in 95% and 90% respectively¹³.

Fluorination of Organic Compounds

Background and Rây's interest :

Fluorine was isolated by Moissan in 1886. Though quite abundant in earth's crust as inorganic fluorides, only a handful of fluoroorganics occur in Nature, like fluoroacetate, a toxin in some plants. On the other hand, synthetic fluoroorganics are now very abundant and their use in industry is crucial and diverse. The C-F bond is 107 kcal/mol strong and add inherent thermal stability to fluoroorganics.

In 1904 Rây visited several major laboratories in Europe to meet masterminds and to pick-up new research ideas and inspiration. In Paris, among other great like Berthelot who had inspired him to undertake the work on Hindu Chemistry, he met Moissan who was famous also for his work his discovery of calcium carbide and artificial diamonds, crystal of which he showed to Rây. He also showed the detailed description of Rây's mercurous nitrite work¹⁴ in his treatise of inorganic chemistry. It is quite likely that this memorable visit had aroused Rây's interest in organic fluorination.

Reagents and choice of thalious fluoride :

Of the many methods now available for fluorination of organic compounds, the use of potent inorganic fluorides is the oldest. Now there are several types of reagents : metal fluorides, ammonium fluorides, *N*-fluoro compounds, fluoroaminosulfuranes and more, the list growing. Coming back to Rây's time Moissan introduced silver fluoride, AgF, as the fluorinating reagent in 1891. In the following year Meslans prepared acetyl fluoride from the chloride using ZnF₂. Later in 1930 both SbF₅ and Hg₂F₂ were introduced by Swarts.

Citing such instances Rây and his group initiated the use of thalious fluoride in 1933. The details of procedure used varied from system to system. But the gross general steps were to mix the precursor halide (chloride, bromide and in some cases iodides) with TIF powder well and

often keeping the mixture at room temperature or in the cold for a few hours. Solvent (ethanol, ether), were required in some cases only. The mixture (precursor halide, TIF and solvent if any) was heated to reflux usually for prolonged periods and finally the fluoro derivative was distilled off and redistilled if required. All precursor halides and the product fluorides studied by Rây's group were liquids. The fluorides were pungent and lachrymatory in general. Their boiling points were significantly lower than those of the halide precursors. They were found colourless in several cases as expected but some had light yellow or brown colour undoubtedly due to presence of impurities though not so stated by the authors. Below we summarise the system made by Rây's group.

Fluoroformate esters :

Though described as fluorocarbonate esters by Rây^{15,16} these are better called as fluoroformate esters, **3**. Attempts to prepare these with AgF, ZnF₂ etc. as fluorinating reagent and chloroformate esters as precursors were unsuccessful, explosive decomposition with evolution of alkyl fluoride took place. On the other hand TIF converted corresponding chloroformates to fluoroformates **3a** and **3b** in 25–50% yield.

Some fluoroketones and fluoroacetal :

In a short note Rây and coworkers described¹⁷ the synthesis of monofluoroacetone **4** using TIF. The monochloro precursor was found unreactive but monoiodoacetone readily afforded **4**. Later the monobromo precursor was found as effective¹⁸ and it yielded **4** in 66% yield. It afforded a microcrystalline semicarbazone.

ω -Fluoroacetophenone, **5**, was obtained in 79% yield from the bromo precursor. It afforded crystalline 1 : 1 adduct with pyridine and quinoline. Fluoroacetal, **6** was similarly made from the bromoanalogue in 55% yield.

Fluoroacetate esters and Rây's comments on TIF :

In his last paper on fluorination by TIF Rây reported¹⁹

the synthesis of fluoroacetate esters **7a** and **7b** which had however been made by others using different fluorinating agents. Rây's synthesis of **7** used bromo precursors. In this paper¹⁹ he also reported the synthesis of benzyl fluoride **8** from the bromide.

TIF was however found not to react with many chloro, bromo and iodo acids, esters, aldehydes, amides etc. and Rây concluded¹⁹ that TIF "is not of so wide an applicability as was supposed by us".

Conclusion

Rây had a long-standing interest in organic chemistry from his days in Edinburgh University (1882-1888) although his main interest pertained to inorganic chemistry which kept him busy throughout his career. Only towards the end (1933-36) he and his group turned seriously to organic synthesis and made some notable contributions in the areas of thioketones and fluoroorganics. Notable is the synthesis of thiocamphor in satisfactory yield for the first time by reacting camphor in cold solution with dry hydrogen sulfide (reagent) and hydrogen chloride (catalyst). The group also invented the use of thallos fluoride as a fluorinating agent using organic halides as precursors. Examples are some fluorocarboxylate esters and fluoroketones. Though original and notable in Rây's time, better methods are now available.

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